

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17602889>

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO TEACHING SPEECH IN THE INITIAL STAGE

Sagindikov Alisher Aleuatdinovich

Ma'mun University Lecturer

Uzbekistan, Khiva city

asagindikov5@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article examines the current problem of implementing modern pedagogical methods and technologies in educational institutions. The necessity of using innovative approaches to improve the educational process and unlock the potential of the individual is emphasized. Information and communication technologies play a special role, changing the organization of interaction between professional communities on a global scale and enriching the system of training specialists with new didactic and methodological tools. The article covers the relationship between technological innovations and the modernization of educational practices.

Keywords: *pedagogical innovative technologies, educational process, speaking skills, task-based learning, interactive approach.*

In modern educational institutions of all levels, the importance of the problem of introducing modern pedagogical methods and technologies is increasing. This is due to the need to improve the educational process and apply innovative approaches to maximize the natural potential of the individual. As Karakozova E.N. and Shamov A.N. note, the development and implementation of new infocommunication technologies significantly changes the organization of interaction between professional

communities on a global scale, as well as transforms the system of training specialists, enriching it with didactic and methodological tools [2; p. 15].

In this context, special attention should be paid to learning technologies such as Task-based learning, which provide the opportunity to choose a problem or situation for discussion during lessons. Task-based learning is a methodology aimed at assimilating foreign language information that forms and develops communication skills and teaches within the framework of a communicative approach (Communicative Language Learning Teaching) [4; c. 89]. Task-based learning (TBL), or task-based learning, is a method that emphasizes students' completion of specific tasks that require language use to achieve specific goals. This approach focuses on practical application of language in a context that is as close to real life as possible, and promotes deeper acquisition of language skills through active participation. The TBL method is based on the principle that language is best studied and applied when used to solve practical problems, not just through studying theoretical aspects such as grammar or vocabulary. The tasks offered within this approach simulate real communicative situations, allowing students to use language to achieve specific results. This can include tasks for planning, discussing, creating presentations, solving problems, or executing projects.

Among the key methodological principles of the interactive approach, the following are distinguished [1; p. 147]:

- changing the traditional role of the teacher in the educational process, transitioning to a democratic style of communication;
- Mutual communication aimed at perceiving and creating authentic information that will be interesting to all participants, in a context relevant to everyone;
- joint activity characterized by the interaction of three elements: the source of information, the recipient, and the situational context;
- reflexiveness of learning, consisting of conscious and critical consideration of actions, their motives, qualities, and results by both the teacher and the learners.

Interactive learning contributes to the formation of communicative skills and abilities, helps to establish emotional connections between students, and also performs an educational function by teaching teamwork and respect for others' opinions.

Among modern teaching technologies, the most in-demand are: information and communication technologies (ICT), computer programming technologies, internet technologies, personality-oriented technologies, language portfolio technology, testing technologies, project technologies, collaborative learning technologies, game technologies, critical thinking development technologies, and communicative-value technologies. There is an opinion that "teaching technology is a systematic method of creating, applying, and defining the entire process of teaching and assimilating knowledge, taking into account technical and human resources and their interaction, setting the task of optimizing the forms of education" [3; p. 22].

Thus, interactive technologies and multimedia play an important role in creating a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, especially in the field of language teaching. Using audio and video materials, online resources, and interactive exercises significantly enriches the learning process, making it more diverse and engaging. Audio and video materials provide students with the opportunity to interact with real language in a live and contextual format. Video lessons, films, series, and documentaries in the language being studied allow students to hear and see how the language is used in various situations, contributing to better understanding of pronunciation, intonation, and cultural context.

REFERENCES

1. Gorkova, N.P. Theory and Practice of Teaching the Russian Language / N.P. Gorkova. - M., 2007. - p.147.
2. Karakozova, S.A., Shamov, A.N. Modern approaches in teaching Russian as a foreign language / S.A. Karakozova, A.N. Shamov. - M., 2023. - p.15.
3. Savelev, V.V. Methods of Teaching and Teaching the Russian Language / V.V. Savelev. - M., 1994. - p.22.
4. Strelsova, I.V. Methods of Teaching Russian: Modern Trends and Approaches / I.V. Strelsova. - M., 2021. - p.89.